

Zia ul Haq Vis –a Vis Pervez Musharraf: A comparative Overview of Politics in Pakistan

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Abstract

Along with the advent of martial law the previous governmental structure enjoys new revolutions under the new thinking governing body. Previous system was framed under the circumstances when Pakistan was passing through the international framed conspiracies' but after the General Muhammad Zial ul haq's advent the world was entering into geopolitical great game. International foreign policies and relations were changing. Near it Afghan-USSR war (1979-88) started and was enlarged for 9 years. Same as soon after the arrival of General Pervez Musharraf world had to face 9/11 game which was affected the world largely and caused great changing's in foreign policies Pakistan as well as worldwide. Pakistan is the country which enjoyed these revolutions directly and pay so much cast in the terms instability in Pakistan. What were circumstances those affected the Pakistan democratically under the civil-military regimes, is try to highlight in this research article.

Keywords: Military Regime, U.S, 9/11 incident, U.N, Taliban Afghanistan.

Introduction

With the starting of seventh decade of 20th century internal and external political situation, circumstances, affairs and matters related to survival of Pakistan became miserable. Special political situation was pitiable. Getting this situation anti-Pakistan and anti-Islam powers tried to tear Pakistan into pieces; and in effort they also succeeded and Pakistan, losing a wing/part (emergence of Bangladesh, December 16th, 1971) had to face a large lose and humiliation all over the world. Indian power declared, today we drowned the "Two Nation Theory" in the Bay of Bengal. Seeing the unrest situation in Pakistan and external powers'

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dangerous glowering on 5th July, 1977, General Muhammad Zia-ul-Haq take over the charge as Martial law administrator and addressed the Pakistani nation at that evening as;-

- 1-Instead of Zulfiqar Ali Bhutto's government a care taker government would be framed.
- 2-President Fazal Elahi will remain president of Pakistan as he was before this.
- 3-Chief martial law administrator will be the head of administration.
- 4-National assembly and provincial assemblies have resolved.
- 5-Constitution is not cancelled instead of some articles those amplification has been checked.
- 6-Provincial chief justices will be the care taker provincial governors.
- 7-Provincial martial law administrators will be the head of provincial administration.
- 8-Elections will be conducted in November (1977) and the charge (of Government) will be hand over to the public selected representatives.
- 9-Political activities are checked till the next ordinance and before the elections these political activities will restore.
- 10-To tackle the circumstances according to time passage ordinance and disciplines will be issued.
- 11-In civil administration all the transfers those were imposed will be reviewed. (Shahid.1993, 215)

On May 6th, 1978 addressing to the *Kisan* (farmer) conference he said:- "there is a hardship in front me that, day and night have only 24 hours, if they have 48 hours all problems related to us resolve; I am not a politician who puts off (dodges) the public's requests. We have several objectives; and we want to solve all complains and pains in no time individually as well as collectively. I am considering essential three things, first, we should diagnose pain, second its cure and third its medicine." (Ibid. 216-17)

On February 10th, 1979, by television he addressed to Pakistani nation as; " I have mentioned the economic change several times; to destroy the economy, nationalization policy with a lot of other factors was involve, of which use was made possible everywhere. According to teachings of Islam both state and citizen have the right of property equally; and the public and private sector both are the parallel powers for function or positive activity for national advantages, without cooperation of one another to catch the destination is impossible."(Ibid. 220)

As it is observed that democracy have not been a smooth sailing in Pakistan. In the situation of dilemma governances remain under the unrealized dreams. Burgeoning defense expenditures as well as virtual immunities of forces from the measures of accountabilities and their continual interferences in the state affairs had been impediments of substantial magnitude in the way of good governance progress. Else it secret decisions for the survival of state or to enlarge a period of the power body are factors chain that keep save it from all kind of opposite activities from internal and external eyes or access. In Pakistan in the name of Democracy all political, social and several other ailments are tried to cure. So that all desired results could be achieved but opposite powers remain engage to defeat their planning so that could get monopoly again and again and remain in power. In this game public opinion cards are called elections.

Election

Although Zia Ul Haq pledged to conduct the elections within 90 days but some serious

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obstacles enlarged it from 1977 to 1985; of which main was Afghan-USSR war 1979-88. This war became a serious reason, lame, excuse and justification to remain the military regime in power. So that Pakistan could be saved geographically from the anti-Pakistan powers activities and conspiracies. Instead of complex regional situation after the mid of 1983 non-party local Bodies started a movement to held election to fulfilled made promised to held elections to restore democracy in Pakistan. Seeing the local Bodies power under public support Zia ul Haq had to announce to conduct the general elections and these elections were conducted in February 1985. After the success in this election Zia ul Haq had to transfer power to the elected representatives. In the successful result of this election Zia ul Haq on March 23rd 1985 nominated and appointed Muhammad Khan Junejo as the Prime Minister of Pakistan. In the result of this success the democratic activities restored and a new era of democracy started with new zeal and zest.

Referendum 1984, Election 1985 and the Eighth Amendment during the General Zia ul Haq's period eventually were decided to hold election in the country for the rehabilitation of democracy for the regional and global entrust but before to hand over the political power to the public representatives, Zia ul Haq by referendum in December 1984 wanted to secure his position as the head of the state.

On December 19th, 1984, it was announced to conduct the referendum. For this referendum a questioner was prepared as;-

i-do you support the recent governmental policies?

ii-do you believe in Ideology of Pakistan and want it protection?

iii-do you support the implementation of Islam?

iv-do you vote for to accelerate and strength this system?

v-do you support the programme announce on August 12th, 1983? (Ibid.,227)

It was the questioner which was impossible to deny by a Muslim. So, the ration of voting for Zia-Government success was 97.71%. In this way General Zia Ul Haq selected the president of Pakistan for next five years by himself. On February 25th, 1985 all over Pakistan National Assembly's and on February 28th, 1985 provincial assemblies' on the base of non-party elections were conducted. Opposition also took part.

To make smooth way for governance Muhammad Khan Junejo was selected as the prime minister of Pakistan. Because Zia ul haq wanted a person' accompany who will have a soft corner for him and could level the way for his governance and desired policies, means "Yes Man". So, he selected Muhammad Khan Junejo for him to keep environment peaceful. Getting advantage of this thing before to hand over the power charge to new elected bodies Zia ul Haq, to save him from all kinds of punishments, managed to retroact the acceptance all his past fair and unfair deeds during last eight years. During his era he also managed several constitutional amendments of which Eighth Amendment was prominently, (Article 58-2b, Constitution of 1973) under which he was granted the "reserve powers" to dissolve the National Assembly and; delegating a lot of powers to the prime minister, president himself got a lot of constitutional and political facilities, powers and authorities and using political umbrella became a dictator. But Zia ul Haq was right in his views because our democratic system is not able to bear global pressure and it had to accept the international conspiracies net which are a trapped against the survival of Pakistan of which we have a long period experience.

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Political Dictatorship

With the passage of time when legislature felt political withholding, political powers started to demand for more freedom and authority with liberty. With the start of 1988 misunderstandings between president and Prime Minister Bench started to spring up.(Omar Noman,1990),.136-38).

On May 29th , 1988, President Muhammad Zia ul Haq used the article 58(2) b; Dissolving National Assembly of Pakistan removed the Prime Minister Muhammad Khan Junejo and once and again according to political thoughts democracy in Pakistan victim to the dictatorship but this time democracy was victim by the political dictatorship and Pakistan started to go back to the stone age but soon after the death of first time Army-dictator then political dictator Muhammad Zia Ul Haq on August 17th, 1988 Pakistan started its political travel upward and democracy started to spring up again because international powers' entrance into Pakistan reopened and their period of prosperity started.

As it is global rule that some strategic and related to defence policies are kept secret from the political bodies access, because a politician has so many reasons to enclose the secrets in front of any pressure; so it is the requisites of national survival that some planning are kept away from political access. Same as at the time of decision to sign the Geneva Accord Muhammad Khan Junejo could not understood global security game strategies and using its power as a prime minister signing the Geneva Accord committed a big related to global security game mistake and Pakistan had to lose some military and related to geographical achievements advantages. So, Zia ul Haq removed the prime minister who was blind to global security game and was used by internal and external ant-Pakistan powers because of which Pakistan had to pass through the blood-sea for a long time after this Muhammad Khan Junejo's decision to sign the Geneva Accord. It is observed that the international super powers USSR declined and USA as a new Super Global Power appeared on the map of the world. With the gaining super power's rank America closed the door from the Pakistan while Pakistan had been a war-safty-shield for America against USSR during whole Afghan-USSR war period 1979-88. Like this several other silent powers were in ambush and were waiting for the end of Zia period.

Critical Review

According to political thoughts dictatorship causes war. In my views it is wrong because in the dictatorship period all political classed lost their facilities to loot the public revenue and started to cry. In this situation they started to involvement in the military governance and blamed that the military governance is against the public freedom; they only created causes for wars, conflicts and domestic unrest and blame the military governance body for it. It is observed that a dictator's always run the governance carefully avoiding all those things which cause for his decline. In the other hand so-called democracy holder always committed the secret deeds and it is try to cover all their bad deeds and show all weakness of a dictator. In fact reality is against it. In the Zia period all anti-Pakistan powers remained fearful Pakistani governance system was running on a best way under a sincere leader who was not acceptable for those who has a lion share in the Pakistan's destruction economically, politically and politically as well as defensibly. In zia period these powers had to do everything legally. So, it was not acceptable for them. So after his death they called him a cruel and dictator.

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Democracy holders should be ashamed of their own misdeeds that who is corrupt, he or they?. Although military regime has some demerits but it is wrong to say that military-regime is not good for national progress or public welfare or for international relations because during all military regimes' Pakistan had a best image.

Musharraf's military regime and democratic balance

The advent of General Pervez Musharraf on October 12, 1999 in politics and dissolved all the political system of Pakistan was the result of Nawaz Sharif the then prime minister of Pakistan's wrong decisions and strict, unlawful and committed the high levels' mistakes and blunders against all the defence system of Pakistan under the shade of anti-Pakistan silent powers' conspiracies umbrella on which military power had to closed the so-called democratic system under which Pakistan was passing through bitter realities related to defence requisites of time. It was necessary to change the system to save the state of Pakistan from the anti-Pakistan's powers political, social and economic conspiracies under which Pakistan's chessboard was being wrapped and the survival of Pakistan was in danger.

On October 17th, '999, a guide line by General Pervez Musharraf was framed. It was 7 points agenda, of which points were as:-

1-rebuilding the National trust and moral;

2-to reinforce the federation and develop the communication and national unity among provinces;

3-to take steps immediately for the economic rehabilitation and restore the traders trust;

4-to convince the law-sovereignty and the availability of Justice in no time;

5-to demolish the political involvement in national institutions;

6-to transfer the power/authority to the basic level, so that public partition in the national affairs could be convinced and;

7-immediately and neutral accountability. (S.M.Shahid.2002., 346)

On October 29th, 1999 a team of Commonwealth foreign ministers visiting Musharraf asked about the rehabilitation of democracy. He replied may be it will take long time returning to its back position.

More about he explained there are some serious causes in the way of the rehabilitation of democracy here. My government has some certain objectives and I want to prefer these objectives than democracy's rehabilitation in Pakistan.

Anyhow internal as well as external anti-Pakistan powers carried on their pressure and effort to rehabilitation the democratic system in Pakistan because in front of martial strategies in a martial period anti-Pakistan's powers' strategies to degrade the Pakistan's political, social, and administrative system fail or check. While in democratic period all powers remain bust easily to damage the Pakistan's image globally in every field of life. So, all local, regional and international powers pressurized Musharraf to lift the martial law and rehabilitate the democracy.

International powers were keeping him to pressurize continues; even March 25th, 2000 Bill Clinton the president of USA visted Pakistan for a short time and revised their request in the shape of order but two days before his arrival on March 23rd, Pervez Musharraf had announced to conduct the elections for the rehabilitation of democracy in Pakistan once and again.

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During a press conference meeting musharraf assured to conduct elections within six months from December 2000 to May 2001 and it will be first round while second round for local election at district level would be conducted in July 2001.

Justifying his decisions, he explained that Democracy will be started here at the district level and local governments will give power to the Governmental administrative structure and step by step provincial and federal elections' process will be completed. (edition.cnn.com/2000)

Pervez Musharraf promised that real democracy will be restored through local elections but he based all his power's policies on the General Muhammad Ayub Khan's Basic Democracies' system imposed in 1962. (www.ciaonet.org/olj/sa/sa_jan01kus01.html)

Facing with trenchant criticism internal and external once and again he promised to conduct elections in July 2001. He visited Thailand on April 3, 2000 representing the Pakistan in five-nation South East Asian cement tying and seeking foreign investments.

New system of local self-government

On March 23rd 2000 first time and then next on August 14th 2000 chief executive General pervez Musharraf presented a programme to hand over authorities to the public-elected representatives. This programme was to transfer the authorities from up to low level. This programme was acted upon under the National Reconstruction Bauru. New system of local self-government was established on the rules of public-centralization. This was based on basic rights and duties and basic services were preferred. The objectives of this plan were to finish the misunderstandings between rural and urban, to develop the human-sources, and with the healthy thinking to convince the establishment of collective-government.

Referendum...2002

On April 30, 2002 General Pervez Musharraf to enlarge its period of presidency for more five years conducted referendum. Chief Election Commission Irshad Hussain Khan announcing it described that with a heavy public mandate Pervez Musharraf has been selected as the president of Pakistan for more five years. In the favour of president 42,804,339 votes are casted while in the four of opposition 883,676 votes are casted.

Questioner

Questioner was as:- "Decision will be your"

i-for the implementation of local government system, reinforcement of democracy, implementation of reforms and sequence and the completion of Quaid-e-Azam's concept, are you agree to select Pervez Musharraf as the president of Pakistan for more next five years?

Yes

No

To legitimize his rule General pervez Musharraf conducted referendum on which including legal and illegal powers started to decline the military popularity, moral, Value, graph observing by national and international media, organizations, commentators and by several other sources in the shape of creating the rational of democracy a best governing system at all then a military regime. In the referendum, according to the Election Commission of Pakistan (ECP) General Pervez Musharraf got 71% but according to the official figures released by the Election Commission of Pakistan, 97.5% votes were in favor of General Musharraf; and 2.5% votes were rejected. (www.newsline.com.pk/NewsMay2002)

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President Pervez Musharraf on the account of his all kinds of policies imposed the General Elections in 2000. Large section of democratic forces, some of which was socially conservative, was barred from taking part in this election. The consequences were as the religious as well as political parties in the forms of MMA were elected in the larger number of 51 seats of National assembly in this election than past. It was dangerous news for west because religious parties were against the American invasion on Afghanistan. In the result of this election Mir Zaffar ullah Khan Jamali elected as the prime minister of Pakistan who entered upon the office till June 2004.

Critical Review

After happening the 9/11 accident of incident America showed its closeness to Pakistan and offered for alliance. At that time we stood with America and a new political friendship period, under a new game theory started. At that General Pervez Musharraf thought and made plan to conduct a referendum to take step into politics. In April 2002 announced for referendum and on April 30, 2002 referendum was conducted and General Pervez Musharraf elected as the president of Pakistan. After this president announced for general elections and convinced for rehabilitate the democracy. So, on October 10th, 2002 elections were conducted. Muslim League -Q under the leadership of Pervez Musharraf succeeded with the 77 seats of national Assembly. In Punjab Assembly this party had majority with 130 seats. In this election Mutahidda Majlis ammel also got 51 seats with religious union. This thing increased the western impatience and constraint because religious parties were against the American invasion on Afghanistan. Muttahidda Majlis Ammel (MMA) was objecting on the Musharraf's Army-Uniform. Chaudhry Shujat Hussain along with MMA conducted meeting, at that Pervez Musharraf convince to put off his Army-uniform till December 2004; and MMA accepted his L.F with some amendments. But on January 1st 2004 when President Pervez Musharraf demanded the Vote of Confidence then MMA stood with Opposition leadership/powers/parties; at that President Pervez Musharraf was furious and on December 24th, 2004 he refused to put off Army-uniform. Mir Zaffar ullah Jamali was also in favour of Putting off General Pervez Musharraf's Army-uniform but some old political relations with American power of Mir Zaffar ullah Jamali caused for his resign from the office of Prime minister. On June 26th, 2004 Chaudhry Shujay hussain took oath as the caretaker prime minister of Pakistan until August 29th, 2004 Shokat Aziz replaced of Chaudhry Shujat Hussain as the prime minister of Pakistan. Moreover on October 6th, 2007 conducting presidential elections and gaining success with 384 votes elected the president of Pakistan. After this his success ignoring the security of state against his political stability a large chain of unending serious accidents was started and with that internal and external pressure compelled pervez Musharraf to put off his Army-uniform. In election 2008 Pakistan People's Party got 89 seats and Muslim League –N got 67 seats. In the result of success in this election PPP on March 25th, 2008 elected Syed Yousuf Raza Gilani as the prime minister of Pakistan. Emergency on November 3rd, 2007 caused to decline for the Pervez Musharraf's throne. During all his reign it is observed that how a circle full with pressure had been revolving around him at last caused his decline and old political game started.

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Conclusion

On July 5th, 1977 Enforcing Martial law General Muhammad Zia ul Haq ascended on throne. His period could be divided into two parts; first, from July 5th, 1977 till December 30, 1985; and second, from December 30, 1985 till August 17th, 1988. In first period all Islamic reforms' renaissance was made once and again locally and globally. At the end of first period and during whole second period finishing the martial law along with several other reforms democratic reforms were made. In the second period because of rehabilitation of democracy every discipline of life took its start again with full zeal and zest; public entrust and moral restored for future and among the developing countries Pakistan made a remarkable economic, social and political progress. (S.M.Shahid.2002., 306-7)

Actually military regime is based on the dictatorship. A dictator runs its governing system without the public support. So, it is not a flexible governing system. This ruling system is strict. It has to continue its flow without public involvement. Some time it has to adopt the policies against the public thinking social, economically or politically. The foreign investors restrain to invest their capital during this period. Although during a military regime develops but without domestic or local powers. Home affairs do not match with this system. The environment in regular life routine seems in tension. Open foreign entrance in every field of life checked. NGOs feel it a new obstacle in their activities way. Some global powers interest and entrust in the governing system cut off. Global powers have to established new treaties; have rebuilt new relations; agreements also have to required new changes; and policies have to re-frame. In this situation all stages and pages internal and external powers try to convince the military power to restore or to rehabilitate the democracy.

With the advent of martial law the previous governmental structure awarded of a new revolution under the new thinking of governing. Previous democratic system was framed under the circumstances when Pakistan was passing through the international framed conspiracies' net but after the General Muhammad Zial ul haq's ascending the throne world was entering into geopolitical great game which had divided the world into blocs and polars. International foreign policies and relations were changing. Near it Afghan-USSR war (1979-88) started and was enlarged for 9 years that brought the cold war to end. Same as soon after the advent of General Pervez Musharraf world had to face 9/11 game which affected the world largely politically and caused the great changing in global policies. Pakistan is also the country which enjoyed these revolutions directly and it had to change its former political and, social and economic structure. These were the circumstances those affected the Pakistan democratically under the civil-military regimes a lot of and caused new governing thoughts under the real democratic system as well as changing global policies and relations' thoughts under joint western powers' global planning. In a way military regimes had been doing as a teacher for the reforming of democratic system and its governing body because after the end of military regimes the democracy possessed or its system holder started their democratic governance under a true democratic thinking and policies and remained a lot of welfare-possessed for public for some time. It is another thing that when they felt powerful themselves or monopoly-possessed then they started to become political dictator and committed mistakes. Because it is observed that between Zia ul Haq and pervez Musharraf Pakistan had to change 11 governments. It is the result of democracy for which these politicians run a race without caring legal and illegal method.

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